

CLASSIFICATION OF NIGERIA WIND ISOPLETHS FOR STRUCTURAL PURPOSES

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ABSTRACT

The paper reviewed the useful details of the Soboyejo Isopleths and the Nigerian Meteorological Agency wind Documentation map produced for Nigeria. Discrepancies were observed in the interpretations given to the data produced by the Agency. The researchers used a mathematical relationship between, the Soboyejo's and the Nigerian Meteorological Agency data to produce results which correspond to 100 year mean recurrent interval. Gumbel Type I distribution model of yearly highest gust was used to analyse the data for some scattered points; while the Microsoft Office Excel was used as the tool for the linear interpolations and extrapolations of the data to subdivide the country into five main categories with a yearly mean of 35 to 42 (Category I), 42 to 45.8(Category II), 45.8 to 50(Category III), 50 to 55(Category IV) and 55 to 56 ms⁻¹ (Category V) respectively. These values correspond with dynamic pressures of 941 to 1088 (Category I), 1088 to 1283(Category II), 1283 to 1535(Category III), 1535 to 1855(Category IV) and 1855 to 1925N/m² (Category V) respectively for various classes. Factors accounting for the geographic location, topographical effects, building size, surface roughness and wind gustiness etc. must be incorporated before the final design loads are computed for various structural systems under consideration.

KEYWORDS: Wind speed, Isopleths, yearly mean, physical structures, distribution model.

INTRODUCTION

Every nation has either developed or is in the process of developing its own codes of practice because its geographical and environmental conditions may be diverse and peculiar to it. It is common practice that in most developing countries such as Nigeria (Auta & Maslennikov, 2006), the design or investigation of physical structures and facilities are in accordance with the requirements of other codes of practice such as the British Standard (BS) at different parts of the World. Countries like India, Russia (SNIIP, 2004) among others have developed their own standards. With the advent of the global satellite mobile (GSM) and the incessant alarm towards the need for the development and use of renewable energies like wind and solar; there is need to update and upgrade the Nigerian Code of Practice to meet the present day needs.

Presently, the Nigerian Standard Code of Practice (NSCP 1 (1973)) is used for the assessment of materials and general wind loadings. It is mainly based on yearly mean recurrent data and serves as a useful tool for structural design of infrastructural facilities. The data required for the design of renewable energies like wind and solar energy usually assume daily data. These reasons clearly show that, data relating to both daily and yearly events such as wind and solar are required for the development and design of many engineering facilities.

The first step that must be taken in order to effectively and efficiently carryout dynamic analysis and design of tall structures; such as telecommunication masts, long span bridges or high-rise buildings which are usually subjected to aerodynamic loadings; is to correctly assess the basic wind speed (V), local to the site where the structures are to be built or constructed. This basic wind speed is usually obtained, through the results of the statistical and probabilistic analyses of the meteorological records of wind speeds known as the isopleths map corresponding to various project locations or localities (i.e. including their local altitudes).

Onundi *et al.* (2009) observed some discrepancies in the interpretations given to the data produced by the Nigerian Meteorological Agency (NIMET). The useful details of the Soboyejo Isopleths and the Nigerian Meteorological Agency wind Documentation maps were used for the interpretations of data produced. The following were achieved:

- (i) Factors varying between 7.78 to 13.00 were recommended to conveniently convert the daily mean records produced by the Nigerian Meteorological Agency to the yearly mean records produced by Soboyejo,

- (ii) The researchers used a mathematical relationship between, the Soboyejo's and the Nigerian Meteorological Agency data to produce results which correspond to 100 year mean recurrent interval.
- (iii) The results of the investigation were strengthened by the Nigerian Meteorological Agency geographic description of meteorological altitudes where the data were observed and obtained. This has provided very useful information for the computation of altitude factors for various localities in the country.

According to Kijewski and Kareem (1998; 2001) and Kijewski *et al.* 1999), many aspects involved in the estimation of wind loads are held in common by the various international codes and standards. Instead of commenting on them repeatedly, they have been highlighted in their work briefly that:

- a) All the standards, subdivided the global terrain into 3 to 5 categories depending on their influence on how they affect the wind characteristics at that location.
- b) The design wind speed, associated with one or a range of mean recurrence intervals, used in analysis by each of the codes is typically the product of the basic wind speed and factors to account for the geographic location, topographical effects, building size and surface roughness, etc.
- c) Wind gustiness introduces dynamic load effects which the codes and standards account for by factoring up the mean loads by a gust factor. Both time and spatial averaging play an important role in the development of gust factors. For a very small size structure, a short duration gust, which completely engulfs the structure, e.g. a 3 – second gust, may be adequate to account for the effects of gustiness, in which case the gust factor is unity.
- d) On the other hand, if the wind-averaging interval is higher, e.g. 10 minutes or more, the averaged wind exhibits less fluctuation, and accordingly the gust factor is greater than unity. This departure from unity is affected not only by the averaging interval, but also by the site terrain and the size and dynamic characteristics of the structure.
- e) Furthermore, it should also be noted that while all of the standards reference their wind speed at 10 m above ground in a flat, open exposure, each uses gusts of different duration. The British and Canadian standards use the mean hourly wind speed in design, while the European Pre standard, the China National Standard and the AIJ Recommendations all use a 10-minute mean wind velocity. The ASCE7-95 standard references a 3 second gust, as does the Australian Standard, though, in the latter case. This wind is later converted to a mean hourly wind for subsequent calculations of dynamic pressure and the gust factor. As a result, for any adequate comparison amongst standards, there must be proper adjustments of the reference velocity.

This paper focuses on the use of the afore-mentioned information, data obtained and mathematical model to categorise Nigeria into five main meteorological classification zones for structural purposes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The information obtained from the Soboyejo Isopleths map (Figure 1) (Soboyejo,1971) and the national communications commission (NCC) report on “Technical Specifications for the Installation of Telecommunications Mast and Towers” (Figure 2) (NCC, 2009), developed for Nigeria were used as the basic data for this investigation. Gumbel Type I (Gumbel, 1954; Jenkinson, 1955) distribution model of yearly highest gust was used to analyse the data for some scattered points in the country; while the Microsoft Office Excel was used as the tool for the linear interpolations and extrapolations of data. Figure 3 shows the corresponding graph and best fit equations of the scattered points for these basic data.

Figure 1: Soboyejo Isopleths Map for Nigeria

Figure 2: Meteorological Agency Wind flow Documentation Map for Nigeria

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. The researchers applied a mathematical relationship ($y = 38.33e^{0.019x}$; $R^2 = 0.998$) between, the Soboyejo's (y - axis) and the Nigerian Meteorological Agency results (x - axis) to produce Figure 3 which corresponds to 100 year mean recurrent interval.
2. The recommendation in (1) was used to classify the Nigerian environment into five main categories and classes as shown in Figures (4 and 5) respectively.
3. The corresponding factors accounting for the geographic location, topographical effects, building size, surface roughness and wind gustiness etc. must be incorporated before the final design loads are computed for various structural systems under consideration.

4. The Soboyejo and NIMET isopleths maps are useful information as wind data for Nigeria. The data relating to altitudes of different locations in the country (Table1) provided additional information needed for a complete structural design of tall structures and multi-storey buildings at different locations in the country.

Figure 3: Isopleths of Wind Speed for Zones in Nigeria

Table 1 – Geographical Description of Meteorological Stations in Nigeria

S/N	STATION NAME	LAT.	LONG.	STATE	ELEVATION
1	YELWA	10.53'N	04.45'E	KEBBI	244.0
2	BIRNI KEBBI	12.28'N	04.13'E	KEBBI	220.0
3	SOKOTO	13.01'N	05.15'E	SOKOTO	350.8
4	GUSAU	12.10'N	06.42'E	ZAMFARA	463.9
5	KADUNA	10.36'N	07.27'E	KADUNA	645.4
6	KATSINA	13.01'N	07.41'E	KATSINA	517.6
7	ZARIA	11.06'N	07.41'E	KADUNA	110.9
8	KANO	12.03'N	08.12'E	KANO	472.5
9	BAUCHI	10.17'N	09.49'E	BAUCHI	609.7
10	NGURU	12.53'N	10.28'E	YOBE	343.1
11	POTISKUM	11.42'N	11.02'E	BORNO	414.8
12	MAIDUGURI	11.51'N	13.05'E	BORNO	353.8
13	ILORIN	08.29'N	04.35'E	KWARA	307.4
14	SHAKI	08.40'N	03.23'E	OYO	
15	BIDA	09.06'N	06.01'E	NIGER	144.3
16	MINNA	09.37'N	06.32'E	NIGER	256.4
17	ABUJA	09.15'N	07.00'E	FCT	343.1
18	JOS	09.52'N	08.54'E	PLATEAU	1780.0
19	IBI	08.11'N	09.45'E	TARABA	110.7
20	YOLA	09.14'N	12.28'E	ADAMAWA	186.1
21	ISEYIN	07.58'N	03.36'E	OYO	330.0
22	IKEJA	06.35'N	03.20'E	LAGOS	39.4
23	OSHODI MET.AGRO	06.30'N	03.23'E	LAGOS	19.0
24	LAGOS (HQ) ROOF	06.27'N	03.24'E	LAGOS	14.0
25	LAGOS (MARINE)	06.26'N	03.25'E	LAGOS	2.0
26	IBADAN	07.26'N	03.54'E	OYO	227.2
27	IJEBU-ODE	06.50'N	03.56'E	OGUN	77.0
28	ABEOKUTA	07.10'N	03.20'E	OGUN	104.0
29	OSHOGBO	07.47'N	04.29'E	OSUN	302.0
30	ONDO	07.06'N	04.50'E	ONDO	287.3
31	BENIN	06.19'N	05.06'E	EDO	77.8
32	AKURE	07.17'N	05.18'E	ONDO	375.0
33	WARRI	05.31'N	05.44'E	DELTA	6.1
34	LOKOJA	07.47'N	06.44'E	KOGI	62.5
35	ONITSHA	06.09'N	06.47'E	ANAMBRA	67.0
36	PORT-HARCOURT	04.51'N	07.01'E	RIVERS	19.5
37	OWERRI	05.29'N	07.00'E	IMO	91.0
38	ENUGU	06.28'N	07.33'E	ENUGU	141.8
39	UYO	05.30'N	07.55'E	AKWA IBOM	38.0
40	CALABAR	04.58'N	08.21'E	CROSS RIVER	61.9
41	MAKURDI	07.44'N	08.32'E	BENUE	112.9
42	IKOM	05.58'N	08.42'E	CROSS RIVER	119.0
43	OGOJA	06.40'N	08.48'E	CROSS RIVER	117.0

Source: (NCC, 2009)

Figure 4: Categorisation of the Prevailing Wind Isopleths into Zones

Figure 5: Classification of Nigeria into Wind Speeds Isopleths Zones

CONCLUSION

1. The Soboyejo and NIMET isopleths maps are still valid information as wind data for Nigeria.
2. The altitudes or elevations in Table 1 are useful data for the country, while the information contained in Figure 2 are sometimes difficult to interpolate to determine the actual corresponding values of prevailing wind speed for locations.

3. For design processes and economy, the country was subdivided into five main categories with a yearly mean of 35 to 42 (Category I), 42 to 45.8(Category II), 45.8 to 50 (Category III), 50 to 55 (Category IV) and 55 to 56 ms^{-1} (Category V) respectively. These values correspond with dynamic pressures of 941 to 1088 (Category I), 1088 to 1283(Category II), 1283 to 1535(Category III), 1535 to 1855(Category IV) and 1855 to 1925 N/m^2 (Category V) respectively for various classes.
4. The factors accounting for the geographic location, topographical effects, building size, surface roughness and wind gustiness etc. must be incorporated before the final design loads are computed for various structural systems under consideration.

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